

“The Magic of Freedom”. How Migrants Went from the „Polish Peasant“ to Coveted Leaders

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1. Foreword

What political freedom can achieve

Among other things, my essay will analyse the concept of freedom, which I will lay out by example of the Polish tradition of Westward migration. If the philosophical interpretation of ontology functions as a collective term for the possibilities and conditions of all existence, I would also like to pose two fundamental questions in my essay, which I will seek to answer in the conclusions:

What does it mean when the most elementary foundation of all existence, which is linked to the concept of freedom, is missing – and when does it become an abstract symbol?’

In doing so, I will develop a throughline that is based on a brief chronological outline of Polish migration to Western countries. At the same time, I will discuss Poland’s current economic boom, which is in part due to the money earned abroad by migrant labourers – especially via remittances and investments at home. In addition, I would like to present the reader with a rich tableau of historical and current facts– in particular the transformation of Znaniecki’s Poles who emigrated to the United States in the 19th century, the so-called “Polish Peasant”, and today’s Polish migrants some of whom have become coveted executives in the West.

Key words:

Freedom –Unfreedom, Piotr Skarga as a Symbol of Polish National Unity, Polish Migration Tradition, Transformation between Then and Now, and Here and There

In 1843, Heinrich Heine wrote the famous lines from his exile in Paris in the poem “Night Thoughts”:

“When I think of Germany at night, / Then I am deprived of sleep...”

This motif of brooding at night about what is existentially important is a hallmark of a literary tradition which people have used to deal with social grievances for centuries – for instance via accusation, criticism or intellectual classification. Therefore, I would like to illustrate the topic of this article against the backdrop of both a historical and contemporary landscape. This perspective also gives rise to my central idea: the

search for answers to the question of how the EU – especially in the context of its Eastward enlargement to Poland – can find a balance between neoliberal economics and the preservation of cultural values of member states without jeopardising the stability of the “European house”. Throughout history, political criticism has seen different heydays.

One person who raised his voice against the weakness of royal power in early modern Poland was the Jesuit and royal confessor Piotr Skarga (1536-1612). In general, the 16th century is portrayed as a time of great cultural prosperity in Poland and as the ‘golden age’ of the statehood of the Rzeczpospolita.

Nevertheless, enlightened writers and activists of this era recognised many mistakes and even registered a decline in moral standards as well as the disappearance of old Polish customs. Skarga stood up for these values throughout his life, for freedom and justice, as well as harmony and justice. Skarga also claimed that freedom is innate and inherent in every human being. (Marszk 2018: 120).

As an energetic advocate for reforms of the Polish-Lithuanian state, he did not criticise the autocratic monarchy in the presence of the king, but the aristocratic republican government – i.e. the power of the Sejm (parliament) and the szlachta (the nobility), both of which he wanted to limit by strengthening the crown. However, his demands remained unfulfilled. Over 150 years later, this contributed to the three partitions of Poland (1772, 1793, 1795), which ended Polish sovereignty until 1918. Full sovereignty was only restored in 1989 with the end of the People's Republic of Poland. During a visit to the Church of St Peter and Paul in Krakow, where Skarga's grave is located, I thought of Skarga again and paused as I prayed in front of his grave. Do we need more “Skarga memorialisers” today? The historical role of Piotr Skarga as an admonisher against political fragmentation and in favour of strong institutions is indeed symbolically relevant in today's Poland, as it creates an echo in the present deadlock between the pro-PiS president Andrzej Duda and the liberal-conservative coalition in power since 2023, which can lead to an institutional standstill of reforms.

As Poles, we are obliged to learn from history, as we have paid dearly for past mistakes. At the beginning of my essay, I would also like to take a brief look at the chapters ahead, while building my line of argument in the direction of philosophy, Kant and eventually raise the question of the concept of freedom.

Piotr Skarga was born in Grójec in 1536 (the fact that he was a Mazovian warrior had an impact on his role in the history of the Polish language, which will be discussed below). He came from a family that claimed to be noble. In the years 1552-1555, he studied at the Krakow Academy and graduated with a bachelor's degree. From 1560 to 1562, he stayed in Vienna as tutor to Jan Tęczyński. After his return, he was ordained a secular priest in 1564 (as paradoxical as this may sound – today the more appropriate term “diocesan priest” is used). However, in 1569 he entered the Jesuit novitiate in Rome and linked his entire future to the expansive and influential Society of Jesus. On his return to the country, he took up a position as a lecturer and preacher at the Jesuit College in Pułtusk and later at the College in Vilnius. When the

Vilnius College was elevated to an academy by decree of King Stefan Batory in 1579, he became the first rector of the Vilnius Academy – today's Vilnius University (Walczak 2012: 173f).

2. Freedom through the prism of philosophy

We come into the world and find it and ourselves in it as it and we are. As Hegel and later Marx remarked, man changes himself and occasionally the world thanks to his skills, but under circumstances that he or she may not have wanted or set. Freedom simply means that we take responsibility for the opinions, knowledge and skills that we acquire and decide for ourselves how we want to position ourselves in life, which unfortunately we did not design ourselves. Nobody does this for us – we should, may and must do it ourselves as soon as we come of age. Promoting the understanding that this self-determination is the great asset of human beings released from the constraints of nature and the social order was the goal of all great progressive thinkers of the past centuries (Beppler-Spahl et al 2023: 5).

A state of consciously perceived “freedom” almost always goes hand in hand with a certain risk, thus opening up new paths, life concepts, encounters and experiments.

Kant coined the motto “*Sapere aude!*” for the Enlightenment. (“Have the courage to use your own reason!”). With his categorical imperative (“Act only according to that maxim which could also be a general law”), however, he established an ethical framework that was intended to regulate the responsible use of the powers of thought and action.

An appropriate understanding of Kant's doctrine of freedom is that it deals with one and the same complex issue, which is considered from two different points of view.

In short, it is about freedom in both speculative and practical terms. Incidentally, in both passages, Kant speaks of freedom in both respects, and he does so in the same way. In the “Canon” it is said, as previously in the “Dialectic”, that it is that (free) volition “which can be determined independently of sensual impulses, that is, by causes of motion which are imagined only by reason”, (practical) freedom also includes a moment of spontaneity, a “causality of reason in determining the will”. The “Canon” shows “dialectics” with regard to transcendental freedom, which it distinguishes from practical freedom by an “indessen” and defines it as something that demands an “independence of this reason itself (with regard to its causality of beginning a series of phenomena) from all determining causes of the world of the senses”. Kant's summation could be understood in such a way that if one seeks to justify freedom in speculative (theoretical) terms, i.e. in terms of its possibility, then one cannot do so without recourse to the transcendental idea of it, with which it stands or falls, as it were. Meanwhile, if freedom is merely understood in practical terms (as a practical concept), then one can ignore this idea; it is literally not needed “practically”. (cf. Geisman 2007: 2).

“...Freedom [...] in the actual meaning as the ability to determine oneself independently of all natural causes] is a mere idea, and to act in accordance with this [...] transcendental] idea is to be free in the practical sense....” (Geisman 2007: 12 cited in Kant MMron Vorl. AA 29.898 m. H. 18,19)¹

The freedom of a will not to be determined by natural laws, but to be able to set a causal chain in motion independently of sensual drives, further implies that the content of the will can be shaped freely – causality from freedom and for freedom. It is this core idea of a freedom that affirms itself that accompanies the Kantian concept (Ellmers 2015: 154).

The symbol of “freedom” after the Holocaust gains its particular tension through existential philosophy. For Sartre, for instance, freedom is the phenomenological ontology par excellence. In Sartre’s dialectic, it is not just a mere attribute, not a quality that, together with others, constitutes the essence of man. The absolute rank of freedom is derived from the fact that it is anchored in the ontological. It is part of the structure of human being, which cannot be understood in terms of substance or essence. Rather, man is characterised by the fact that he is and can only be by determining himself through acts of freedom and in this way striving to create an essence for himself. Thus, for Sartre, the human being is the being in which “existence precedes essence”; the being that “exists first, encounters itself, emerges in the world and then defines itself.” For Sartre, however, this gives freedom a greatness that cannot be ignored. In everything that belongs to being human, it must be included in the consideration as the defining moment par excellence. Since man only exists by designing himself in freedom, he is not free not to design himself. He cannot escape being continuously determined by acts of his choice, i.e. to become who he will be in the future. He is “condemned to be free” (cf. Thurnher 71ff).

“The freedom to be free” was a postulate of Hannah Arendt, which also contains a political challenge. One cannot talk about politics without talking about freedom, and one cannot talk about freedom since it also coincides with action: As long as one acts, one is free, not before and not after, because acting and being free are one and the same (Arendt 2014: 1ff). Hannah Arendt’s concept of political freedom is based on her historical preoccupation with revolutions, starting with the liberation movements against imperialism. Freedom proves itself in “public affairs”, and Hannah Arendt’s concept of freedom is certainly Greek-Roman in nature. The public sphere is seen as a venue for the exchange of arguments.

The agora is seen as an arena of debate (Arendt 2018). Similarly, Adorno coined concepts of freedom in the wake of the Nazi dictatorship that critically analysed political ideologies, power structures and social constraints. His understanding of freedom is not an affirmative commitment to ideologies, but a dialectical reflection that analyses the structural conditions of post-war society. To this end, Adorno locates freedom between the poles of state, society and the individual (Adorno 1966).

¹ As the original text that are difficult to translate.

2.1 Lack of freedom - determinants of the Polish historical dilemma

The previous considerations on concepts of freedom open up a dichotomy that corresponds with the opposite pole – namely the concept of unfreedom – thus directing the focus to political unfreedom.

Poland's history between the 14th and 20th century is characterised by external hegemonic powers (Prussia, Russia, Austria, later Nazi Germany and the USSR) and internal structural weaknesses. The loss of Silesia began as early as the 12th century and continued well into the 18th century. The aristocratic republic (1569-1795) failed due to its unanimity principle (*Liberum Veto*), which obstructed reform efforts, as well as the interference of neighbouring powers, which led to complete partition in 1772-1795. The period from 1918 to 1939 was marked by a brief episode of independence, before Poland once again came under foreign rule from 1939 to 1989 (cf. Cegielski / Kądziała 1990).

The consequence of this is a unique European phenomenon: Poland was occupied by various foreign countries for several centuries, thus triggering a national tragedy and a mass exodus Westward. These historical traumas may have shaped a “migraton gene” through epigenetic and transgenerational transmission, which manifests itself in a persistent lack of spatial roots – a condition that symbolises a kind of “wandering” to this day.

2.2 On the move. Polish transcultural migration

Simmel (1903) discussed the question of “how migration of one part affects the form of the whole, otherwise sedentary group” and differentiated between the respective groups of migrants. The positive (constructive), fundamental and centripetal forces of the spatial movement consist of students, executives, workers and teachers. According to Simmel, the more antagonistic, destructive forces include wanderers, e.g. vagabonds and adventurers (cf. Pries 2001: 7). For more than 200 years, there have been regular migration flows from Poland, mostly to Western Europe and the United States. Polish migrants are an integral part of Polish history. There is hardly a family in Poland in which at least one family member has not migrated (Boski 2010a: 510). Therefore, the tradition of Polish migration will be taken up here in a low-threshold manner in order to illustrate a shortcoming in the foundations of human existence – particularly with regard to freedom (choice of employment, social security and self-determination). The protagonists embody a certain type of existence, as they live “in-between and nowhere” in Western Europe and the United States, which certainly can be seen as a challenge: they are caught between different cultural affiliations, economic constraints and the struggle for social recognition.

In the early 20th century, Thomas and Znaniecki produced the first empirical, social-scientific research results when it comes to the emigration of Polish farmers to the Prussian part of Poland as well as to the United States of America (cf. Thomas / Znaniecki 1918, Zaretsky 1995).² The 20th century brought a new upswing in labour

² ‘The Polish Peasant in Europe and America’ is the world's first major empirical study on migration and at the same time the birth of biographical research and “the founding work” (Zaretsky 1996, IX). The outstanding significance of the study lies in the fact that it uses the empirical case of Polish migrants to address the disintegration of the culture of origin (as a disorganisation of primary groups) and the active creation of a new

migration and is widely regarded as the “age of migration”. However, the question is not about increasing or decreasing processes of migration, but rather their linkages to intercultural paradigms, thus illustrating a qualitative differentiation of population strata that participate in migration (cf. Castles / Miller 2003). The geographical focus of Polish labour migration has changed in recent years. While destination countries such as Germany, the United Kingdom, the Benelux countries, the United States and Canada have historically played a central role. Since Poland’s accession to the EU in 2004, there has been a dynamic in two different directions: On the one hand, Germany and the Benelux countries continue to be traditional destination countries for commuter migration. In Germany, demographic change, recruitment problems, shortage of skilled labour is costly for the economy, for instance. Orders can no longer be accepted, recruiting staff becomes more expensive and jobs remain unfilled for a long time. The problem is affecting numerous sectors of the German economy and is becoming more acute. On the other hand, there are workers from abroad who would like to work in Germany (Der Weg ausländischer Ingenieure auf den Arbeitsmarkt | VDI, accessed 2 May 2025). It thus becomes clear that this “scene” is no longer dominated by the “desperate, unworldly Polish peasant” of the early 20th century, but by a fundamentally cosmopolitan, smart Polish migrant of 2025, who is driven by political freedoms, economic opportunities and social mobility.

Today’s Polish migrants have been able to thrive both in a free Poland and the world for over 30 years – after centuries of foreign rule. Since 1989, Poland has developed into a sovereign state whose citizens can make their own decisions about their future in a democratic system. The phrase “the right to decide in one’s own house” symbolises the national and individual self-determination that has been achieved. The integration of skilled labour from different countries has become an integral part of business life. In this context, Polish managers have taken on an increasingly important role in German companies.

The current rise in migration from Poland to Western countries – particularly since the EU’s freedom of movement for workers and increasingly in the last five years – includes skilled workers and managers who work primarily in the caregiving, medical and construction sector, as well as increasingly qualified workers in other shortage occupations.

Many Polish managers have an excellent education and have gained experience both in Poland and internationally. This makes them valuable assets for German companies, especially in industries where expertise and specialisation are in demand. (The role of Polish executives in German companies | Find a Polish employee, accessed 29 April 2025). Poland has also built a strong engineering tradition in recent years, with renowned technical universities and colleges offering a solid education in engineering and technology. Polish engineers are known for their high level of expertise, analytical skills and innovative approach to complex projects, which is why they are in high demand in Western Europe. (Polish engineers and technicians – indispensable for German industry | Gastamo Polish Employment Agency, accessed 29 April 2025).

social and cultural affiliation as an experience of crisis, in which objective circumstances and the subjective attitudes and expectations of migrants intertwine and clash contradictorily (cf. Strübing 2012: 99).

Across the world, the German healthcare system has a good reputation: well-trained medical staff, modern technical equipment and comparatively short waiting times for patients. According to the German Medical Association, a total of 58,168 foreign doctors were registered in Germany in 2019, of whom 2,136 were from Poland. Thanks to the EU Professional Recognition Directive, it is generally not hard for Polish medical graduates to get their training certificates recognised in order to be employed in Germany (Polish doctors are moving to Germany - Goethe-Institut Polen, accessed on 29 April 2025). According to official figures, more than 20,000 doctors have emigrated in the past 20 years, accelerated by Poland's accession to the EU in 2004. However, fewer and fewer have left recently. "We are dependent on Polish colleagues", explains Daniela Kleeberg, site manager at the Görlitz-based Malteser Hospital St. Carolus, where a third of staffers comes from Poland (Pandemic accelerates brain drain: Why Polish doctors are leaving their home country, accessed on 2 May 2025). Polish engineers also enjoy a good reputation among German employers. They value them for their expertise, their commitment and their ability to think outside the box. They can also lead large groups effectively (Polscy inżynierowie w Niemczech - Wirtualne Niemcy, accessed on 2 May 2025).

3. On forgetting and remembering

Remembering forgetting – this phrase sounds paradoxical. How can one remember something that has just slipped from one's memory? On closer inspection, however, this is by no means impossible. The church father Augustine dedicated the 10th book of his "Confessions" to remembrance and also dealt with forgetting, whereby he immediately noticed this paradox: "What do I want to say if I am certain that I remember my forgetting? Should I say something, that it is not in my memory, which I do remember?" (Assmann 2011.1f).

When it comes to collective imprints of a national memory, there will always be differences and similarities between individuals, different ways of remembering and forgetting that are typical of a particular time, society and group (cf. Meier1996: 62). Sensitivity can vary greatly depending on the situation. Below, I would like to offer some hypothetical questions about abstract concepts such as the "house", generational communication and memory, which could have potential causal connections to Poland's painful history.

- What if we had our "house" all to ourselves again, unoccupied by strangers? How would our lives have been organised then?

- How can generations talk about this? What narratives could emerge and how was it talked about in families?

- How did they remember the times of unfreedom, and how did they ultimately process or forget the burdens?

For Luhmann, such questions, which are located in a contrasting horizon between remembering and forgetting, could potentially correspond to systems of consciousness and the communication system of a society. It is not surprising that Luhmann finds a key concept of his systems theory approach in his "foster father"

Parsons, namely in the concept of double contingency.³ Double contingency can be a starting point for the self-organisation of a social system. As part of the analysis of the problem of double contingency and the systematisation of sociology as a twofold social theory and analysis, this article also emphasises the significance of the basic concept of asymmetrisation, a definition of the functions of the attribution of freedom for communication systems, a new version of the differentiation of system-theoretical levels – including a proposal for the differentiation of factual, social and temporal subsystems of society – as well as a clear distinction between structural and system differentiation (Kärtner 1990: 60).

General systems theory is based on the premise that “there are self-referential systems” (Luhmann 1984: 31), while specifying this notion in its system typology according to the specific “type of operation” (Luhmann 1984: 61): In addition to, for instance, chemical, physical and living systems, there are also self-referentially closed systems of meaning, namely systems of consciousness as well as a society’s communication system. Within a given society, there is a historical differentiation of self-referentially closed communicative subsystems. On the basis of the theorem of the self-referential closedness of systems of meaning that differentiate between actuality and potentiality, the mere mutual orientation of two systems of meaning towards each other becomes the basic problem to be solved in the formation of social order (Kärtner 1990: 63).

So far, this article has made reference to the historical symbolism of two formative historical figures: the German poet Heinrich Heine on the one hand and the Polish Jesuit intellectual Piotr Skarga on the other. In addition, I will take a look at the “umbrella organisation” of all scientific disciplines, namely philosophy. Here, a new thought is introduced which deals with the concepts of freedom and – as its necessary counterpart – unfreedom. The latter is briefly mentioned in order to draw a line to the Polish tragedy, in which the country disappeared from the map of Europe for centuries.

A short timeline of transnational migration from Poland to the West emphasises two concise synonyms: the “Polish peasant” of the early 20th century contrasts with the Polish migrants of 2025, from whom cosmopolitan leaders are now emerging. The aspects of remembering and forgetting are analysed in the context of transgenerational transmission of trauma, with the metaphor of remembering and forgetting serving as an analytical lens.

Up to this point, arguments have been introduced from which certain leitmotifs can be derived, embodied by the protagonists, who are almost national heroes, Heinrich Heine and Piotr Skarga. It is safe to say that both men were concerned about the state of their respective home countries in both their literary and political works. I will then try to explain in an understandable way which philosophical interpretations of the term “freedom” are possible. The opposite pole of freedom, unfreedom, is illustrated by Poland’s historical dilemma that has been repeated several times in

³ Finally, the concept of contingency refers to the behavioural expectation of the meaning systems for themselves and the other as well as the expectation of this expectation. Sense system 1 assumes that its behaviour, like the behaviour of sense system 2, is contingent and that sense system 2 also assumes this. And both assume this in turn. Luhmann therefore speaks of double contingency (Kärtner 1990: 64)

history. These circumstances have resulted in the ongoing labour migration to the West.

The interaction between forgetting and remembering creates the collective memory of a people that continues centuries-long migratory movements and perhaps even possesses a “migration gene”. Do Poles have migration in their blood? In addition, other aspects will be developed at least partially in the further course of the text, as the Polish peasant migrant of the early 20th century transforms into a smart and cosmopolitan leader – a modern migrant from Poland. From now on, we will deal with the possible effects of long periods of occupation, in which a nation and its people – using Poland as an example – “inherits” a transgenerational, collective trauma that is reproduced again and again and leads to a feeling of “nicht einrasten können”.

3.1 Trauma

Wars, deportations, occupations and genocides cause an exodus of peoples and mass emigration. Migration is a sudden and holistic change in a person’s geographical, social and cultural environment. Migration also is a social and psychological multi-generational process. The continuity of the biography is constituted by an overarching perspective on the connection between the past and the present. The psychological upheaval caused by migration results from the need to cope with four psychological processes at the same time, each of which is very stressful in itself:

- the processing of grief, which encompasses all areas of life: grief for countless losses, relationships, material objects of love, places, symbols, personal skills and abilities that have now become worthless;
- a state of “multiple traumata”, as learning processes take place in all conceivable areas of life, while the migrant cannot rely on the ‘familiar’, and the psyche, especially the perception, is overwhelmed by an unmanageable amount of external stimuli;
- the pressure to perform and adapt to the immigration society and its institutions (workplace, offices, etc.);
- experiences of exclusion, discrimination and the hostile reactions of the host society, countless narcissistic insults (cf. Kürşat 315ff).

Transmission, this is how Freud calls this process of “emotional inheritance”. This raises the question of what distinguishes generations from each other and what connects them and which unconscious transmission of experiences between parents and children may be at play. For instance, there could also be an unintentional passing on of (extreme) traumatisation to the offspring (cf. More 2013: 1).

For the sociologist Karl Mannheim, on the other hand, when he discussed both the complexity and significance of generational phenomena and the relationship between sociological and biological understanding in 1928, it was still clear that “the generational phenomenon [...] is one of the fundamental factors in the emergence of historical dynamics” (Mannheim 1928, p. 565). From his point of view, the transmission and transfer of inherited cultural assets included not only conscious and teachable content, but also “attitudes to life, emotional content, attitudes that are

unconsciously, unintentionally inherited and transferred” (ibid., p. 538) (cf. More cited in Mannheim 2013:5). Traumatic experiences that cannot be processed and integrated by those affected not only remain a lifelong burden for them. They are also reflected in the dreams, fantasies, self-image, emotional experiences, unconscious experiences and unconscious behaviour of their offspring. For instance, in the case of mental illness of the parents, experiences of maltreatment and abuse, as well as experiences of war or torture, transgenerational transmission phenomena in future generation may occur.

Today’s biomolecular research results prove that wars, persecution, deportation and genocide clearly do not pass without leaving behind not only physical but also, above all, psychological traces in the descendants, thus fatefully implanting the resulting traumatising in the psyche of future generations. When it is not possible to come to terms with the trauma, or only incompletely, the emotional legacy becomes a burden for grandchildren and great-grandchildren (ibid. 27).

To date, no empirical studies have been published that explicitly relate to a specific ethnic group and comprehensively investigate the transgenerational transmission of trauma to subsequent generations. However, a hypothetical question may arise, for instance in relation to Poland: Could it be that we Poles – after centuries of foreign rule and repeated deportations – have inherited a “migration gene” from our ancestors that continually pushes us to migrate even after 30 years of freedom? Poland’s history is indeed unique in Europe: over the past almost 600 years,⁴ the country has been repeatedly occupied by various foreign powers – from the partitions in the 18th century, through the occupations in the 19th and 20th century, to the end of communism in 1989. Each of these crises have led to massive waves of emigration to Western Europe, the United States and South America.

3.2 Illusion

Every such exceptional situation not only deeply shakes the physical level of human existence. This experience of being human can also give rise to inner images. With the help of inner images, known as illusions⁵, the psyche searches for curable motives in order not to break. To this day, deeply religious Poles search for their “imagos” in their approach to Christian spirituality, which has accompanied them through their painful history. I remember that my paternal grandmother always lit a candle on her family altar so that the fire would not go out during the day, because the candlelight was supposed to protect us from negativity.

In Kant’s world, the spiritual, creative forces have a “sphere of activity” in which they can act not rationally but imaginatively. The subject here is in fact not merely sovereign, but (in contrast to the inert subject of empiricism) extremely lively and active; since it is endowed with all the productive energy of an epistemological entrepreneur. It is now a matter of maintaining this creative energy without overriding

⁴ This partition of Poland took place 424 years earlier than the other partitions that sealed the end of Poland in the 18th century. On 7 April 1348, Charles IV of Luxembourg incorporated Silesia and Lusatia into the crown of the Kingdom of Bohemia, although the Duchy of Schweidnitz-Jauer was still de facto independent at this time. In his act of 7 April 1348, issued as Roman and Bohemian King, the monarch proclaimed, among other things, the crown of the Kingdom of Bohemia (Coronae Regni Bohemiae) and included Silesia and later Upper Lusatia in it (Wyrozumski 2004).

⁵ The introverted dream world like the illusion, as Böhne describes it (2024: 248).

the realm of the objective that ensures its significance. Kant therefore emphasises precisely the structure of subjective experience which points beyond itself to the reality of the material external world. The productive activity of this subject secures objectivity instead of undermining it. It no longer cuts the branch on which it is sitting. If the essence of subjectivity is freedom, then the bourgeois man, at the height of his power, seems to be condemned to blindness towards himself, since freedom is, by definition, unrecognisable. What can be recognised is the determinate, and of subjectivity we can say with certainty that it is certainly not. The subject, the founding principle of the entire enterprise, slips through the net of its representation and appears in all its uniqueness only as a silent epiphany or as a “pregnant silence”. If the world is a system of recognisable objects, then the subject that recognises these objects can be in the world any more than (according to a remark by the early Wittgenstein) the eye can become an object within its own field of vision. The subject is not a phenomenal entity that can be attributed to the objects between which it moves, since it brings such objects to their presence in the first place and therefore moves in a completely different sphere. The subject is not a phenomenon in the world, but also embodies a transcendental perspective. We can look at it from the side, so to speak, when it shows itself with the things it represents, but like the ghostly other (cf. Schwarzfischer 2019: 76f).

Sociology is also concerned with the human ability to relate to things that cannot be sensually experienced in the here and now (or at all), i.e. to transcend the level of sensory experience with the help of an ability that has sometimes been described as fantasy, sometimes as imagination. On closer inspection, however, it quickly becomes clear that we are confronted with the imaginary on a daily basis and in a wide variety of environments. We deal with it everywhere and use it as a source of inspiration when we design, plan, daydream, invent, but also use symbols or endeavour to fill in what we do not know about a counterpart with our own assumptions and suppositions (Herbrik 2011, accessed on 3 May 2025, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-531-19797-5_13). Sartre’s work “On the Imagination” thematically summarises problems of emotion and image theory from Husserl’s concept of intentionality and develops a common systematic approach to their classification in the theory of consciousness. Thus, in the “Outline of a Theory of Emotions”, emotion is understood as a mode of consciousness that is essentially characterised by the escape from the world of reality and the construction of a “magical” world of its own (Merks-Leinen 1974:323).

The symbolic and the real will always mean a demarcation for humans. Depending on our life situation, we create dichotomies, a quasi black-and-white way of thinking, from which the imaginary and illusions could originate. These are at the same time substitute solutions for everything that cannot succeed in everyday life and in life concepts, where our alternatives to the present are situated. They also remind us of life’s hardships, of the fragility of all that exists and of the astonishing gift of the human mind to be able to create the “imago”. The individual freedom of thought plays a central role here, through which we were able to read philosophical interpretations at the beginning of the text and which can be interpreted in different ways.

4. Conclusions

At the end of my essay, I would like to offer some answers in relation to the questions I posed at the beginning. What does it mean when the most elementary foundation of all existence, which is linked to the concept of freedom, is missing – and when does it become an abstract symbol? Then a deep-rooted popular belief of Catholicism comes into play, from which our previous generations drew courage, strength and perseverance. In times when we Poles no longer had a home, the effectiveness of our resilience was determined by two concepts: family and church. These two foundations of meaning – especially in times when meaningfulness itself was in question – gave us family life as a physical form of existence and thus the strength to survive all occupying powers. The division of what can result from *sacrum* and *profanum* made life worthwhile for millions of Poles during times of unfreedom. To this day, the layer that makes up the sacred is a fixed cultural standard of Polish society: deep-rooted Catholicism, which embodies not only dogma, but above all faith in the positive and which characterises us Poles even today.

For us, it was more than “imagination” in the sense of Kantian metaphysics. Rather, ritualised, collective practices made us a community (*polis*)⁶ in the past and still to do so today – the community *par excellence*, which shapes its reality by also drawing from spiritual sources to this day.

One of the founding fathers of Europe, Jean Monnet, is credited with saying: “If you had to do it all over again, I would start with culture.” The sentence is regarded as an expression of the realisation that culture is an important driver of European unification. [...] “Each state is responsible for its own cultural policy. The EU supports the member states in preserving cultural diversity and heritage...” (Monnet 2020).

The cultural diversity of the so-called “European house” largely follows a common economic line, that is neoliberalism. However, European nations differ significantly from one another when it comes to cultural diversity, as they each have been shaped by different historic episodes and characteristics – such as the differences between the newly associated Eastern European countries and the Western European states. For its part, cultures are no longer perceived as blocks or circles, but as complex, changeable, interactive networks without fixed boundaries that interpenetrate and flow into one another (<https://kulturshaker.de/kulturkonzepte/transkulturalitaet/>, accessed on 4 May 2025). Transcultural citizens of the 21st century therefore have two “legs” in the globalised world: one “leg” is the “takeoff leg” with which today’s actors can switch between transcultural spaces. The other is the “supporting leg” that provides stability by holding on to a traditional value (cf. Welsch 2017, 2024).

⁶ The reference to the metaphor ‘polis’ is made by Mannheim, Karl (1980): *Strukturen des Denkens*. Frankfurt a. Main: Suhrkamp.

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